

FRACTIONAL DIFFUSIVE WAVES*

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By fractional diffusive waves we mean the solutions of the so-called time-fractional diffusion-wave equation. This equation is obtained from the classical D'Alembert wave equation by replacing the second-order time derivative with a fractional derivative of order $\beta \in (0, 2)$ and is expected to govern evolution processes intermediate between diffusion and wave propagation when $\beta \in (1, 2)$. Here it is shown to govern the propagation of stress waves in viscoelastic media which, by exhibiting a power law creep, are of relevance in acoustics and seismology since their quality factor turns out to be independent of frequency. The fundamental solutions for the Cauchy and signaling problems are expressed in terms of entire functions (of Wright type) in the similarity variable. Their behaviors turn out to be intermediate between those found in the limiting cases of a perfectly viscous fluid and a perfectly elastic solid. Furthermore, their scaling properties and the relations with some stable probability distributions are outlined.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this note is to outline the role of fractional calculus in providing evolution processes of some relevance in acoustics and seismology, which are intermediate between diffusion and wave propagation. In this respect a family of evolution equations is considered starting from the standard diffusion equation (or the D'Alembert wave equation) in which the first-order (or the second-order) time derivative is replaced by a fractional derivative of order β with $0 < \beta \leq 2$, namely

$$\frac{\partial^\beta w}{\partial t^\beta} = a \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}, \quad a > 0, \quad 0 < \beta \leq 2, \quad (1.1)$$

where $x \in S \subset \mathbf{R}$ and $t \in \mathbf{R}^+$ denote the space and time variables, respectively. In (1.1) $w(x, t)$ is the response field variable, and a is a positive constant of dimensions $L^2 T^{-\beta}$. The

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fractional derivative, assumed to be coincident with the standard derivative when the order is an integer, is defined in Caputo's sense, i.e.

$$\frac{\partial^\beta w}{\partial t^\beta} := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} \int_0^t \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} w(x, \tau) \right] \frac{d\tau}{(t-\tau)^\beta}, & \text{if } 0 < \beta < 1, \\ \frac{1}{\Gamma(2-\beta)} \int_0^t \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \tau^2} w(x, \tau) \right] \frac{d\tau}{(t-\tau)^{\beta-1}}, & \text{if } 1 < \beta < 2, \end{cases} \quad (1.2)$$

where Γ denotes the Gamma function.

For the sake of convenience we refer the reader to the Appendix where the essentials of fractional calculus are presented with a discussion about the role of the fractional derivative in Caputo's sense.

It should be noted that (1.1)–(1.2) can be written as a fractional integral equation as follows: if $0 < \beta \leq 1$

$$w(x, t) = w(x, 0^+) + \frac{a}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) (t-\tau)^{\beta-1} d\tau; \quad (1.3)$$

if $1 < \beta \leq 2$

$$w(x, t) = w(x, 0^+) + tw_t(x, 0^+) + \frac{a}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) (t-\tau)^{\beta-1} d\tau. \quad (1.4)$$

As a matter of fact the evolution Eq. (1.1) with (1.2) turns out to be a linear Volterra integro-differential equation of convolution type with a weakly singular kernel of Abel type. Equations of this kind have been treated, both with and without reference to the fractional calculus, by a number of authors.^{1–16} For recent reviews on related topics we refer to Refs. 17 and 18.

In Sec. 2 we derive the general evolution equation governing the propagation of uniaxial stress waves, in the framework of the dynamical theory of linear viscoelasticity. For a power-law solid exhibiting a creep law proportional to t^p ($0 < p < 1$) the evolution equation is shown to be of type (1.1) with $\beta = 2 - p$, henceforth with $1 < \beta < 2$.

In Sec. 3 we review the analysis of the fractional evolution Eq. (1.1) in the general case $0 < \beta < 2$. We first analyse the two basic boundary-value problems, referred to as the *Cauchy* problem and the *signaling* problem, by the technique of the Laplace transforms and we derive the transformed expressions of the respective fundamental solutions (the Green functions). Then, we carry out the inversion of the relevant transforms and we outline a *reciprocity relation* between the Green functions in the space-time domain. In view of this relation the Green functions can be expressed in terms of two interrelated *auxiliary functions* in the similarity variable $r = |x|/(\sqrt{at}^\nu)$, where $\nu = \beta/2$. These auxiliary functions can be analytically continued in the whole complex plane as entire functions of Wright type.

In Sec. 4 we outline the scaling properties of the fundamental solutions and we exhibit their evolution for some values of the order β . For $1 < \beta < 2$ the behavior of the fundamental solutions turns out to be intermediate between diffusion (found for a viscous fluid) and wave-propagation (found for an elastic solid), thus justifying the attribute of *fractional diffusive waves*.

Finally, in Sec. 5 we show how the fundamental solutions can be interpreted as probability density functions related to certain Lévy stable processes with index of stability depending on β .

2. Viscoelastic Waves and the Time-Fractional Diffusion-Wave Equation

According to the elementary one-dimensional theory of linear viscoelasticity, the medium is assumed to be homogeneous (of density ρ), semi-infinite or infinite in extent ($0 \leq x < +\infty$ or $-\infty < x < +\infty$) and undisturbed for $t < 0$.

The basic equations are known to be, see e.g., Refs. 7, 19–21,

$$\sigma_x(x, t) = \rho u_{tt}(x, t), \quad (2.1)$$

$$\epsilon(x, t) = u_x(x, t), \quad (2.2)$$

$$\epsilon(x, t) = [J_0 + \dot{J}(t)*]\sigma(x, t). \quad (2.3)$$

Here the suffices x and t denote partial derivation with respect to space and time respectively, the dot ordinary time-derivation, and the star integral time-convolution from 0 to t . The following notations have been used for the field variables: u for the displacement, σ for the stress, ϵ for the strain. Furthermore, $J(t)$ denotes the *creep compliance* (the strain response to a unit step input of stress); it is assumed to be a non-negative, non-decreasing function of time, with initial value $J_0 := J(0^+) \geq 0$, called the instantaneous (or glass) compliance.

The evolution equation for the *response variable* $w(x, t)$ (chosen among the field variables: the displacement u , the stress σ , the strain ϵ or the particle velocity $v = u_t$) can be promptly derived from the basic equations (2.1)–(2.3), noting that

$$u_{xx} = \epsilon_x = (J_0 + \dot{J}*)\sigma_x = (J_0 + \dot{J}*)(\rho u_{tt}). \quad (2.4)$$

If $J_0 \neq 0$ we introduce the constant

$$c = 1/\sqrt{\rho J_0}, \quad (2.5)$$

and the function (*rate of creep*)

$$\psi(t) := \frac{1}{J_0} \frac{dJ(t)}{dt} \geq 0, \quad t > 0. \quad (2.6)$$

so from (2.4) the evolution equation turns out to be

$$\{1 + \psi(t)*\} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}. \quad (2.7)$$

This is a generalization of D'Alembert wave equation in that it is an integro-differential equation where the convolution integral can be interpreted as a perturbation term. The constant c is the *wave-front velocity*, as it can be proved working in the domain of the Laplace transform.¹⁹ In our opinion the adoption of the technique of the Laplace transforms make easier the investigation of the properties of the solutions of (2.7); in particular, by

this technique Buchen & Mainardi⁴ and Mainardi & Turchetti²² have provided wave-front expansions for the solutions.

Here we use the following notation for the Laplace transform of a function $f(t)$, locally summable for $t \geq 0$, $\mathcal{L}[f(t); s] := \int_0^\infty e^{-st} f(t) dt = \tilde{f}(s)$, $s \in \mathbf{C}$, and we adopt the sign \div to denote a Laplace transform pair, i.e., $f(t) \div \tilde{f}(s)$. Then, the quantity relevant for our purposes turns out to be the complex function

$$\mu(s) := s[\rho s \tilde{f}(s)]^{1/2}, \quad (2.8)$$

which is real and positive for s real and positive. As a matter of fact, $\mu(s)$ turns out to be an analytic function of s over the entire s -plane cut along the negative real axis; the cut can be limited or unlimited in accordance with the particular viscoelastic model assumed. Then the wave-like behavior of (2.7) is proved from the limit

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mu(s)}{s} = \sqrt{\rho J_0} := \frac{1}{c}, \quad \text{Re } s > 0. \quad (2.9)$$

If $J_0 = 0$ we limit ourselves to consider the so-called *power-law solid*, see e.g., Refs. 23, 19, 5 and 7 for which the creep compliance can be written, in our notation, as

$$J(t) = \frac{1}{\rho a} \frac{t^p}{\Gamma(p+1)}, \quad 0 < p \leq 1, \quad t > 0, \quad (2.10)$$

where a is a positive constant whose dimensions are $L^2 T^{p-2}$. For this case we obtain $\mu(s) = s^{1-p/2} / \sqrt{a}$ so

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mu(s)}{s} = 0, \quad \text{Re } s > 0. \quad (2.11)$$

This means that the wave-front velocity is infinite, so the evolution equation corresponding to (2.4) with $J_0 = 0$ exhibits a diffusion-like behavior.

Buchen & Mainardi⁴ have pointed out that in general the wave like or diffusion like character of the evolution equation (2.4) can be investigated in the Laplace domain, see (2.8), by taking into account the asymptotic representation of the creep compliance for short times,

$$J(t) = J_0 + O(t^p), \quad J_0 \geq 0, \quad 0 < p \leq 1 \quad \text{as } t \rightarrow 0^+. \quad (2.12)$$

For the *power-law solid* (2.10) we obtain in (2.4) $J_0 = 0$ and $\dot{J} = t^{p-1} / [\Gamma(p)\rho a]$. As a consequence, the corresponding evolution equation turns out to be of type (1.1),

$$\frac{\partial^\beta w}{\partial t^\beta} = a \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}, \quad \text{with } 1 \leq \beta = 2 - p < 2, \quad (2.13)$$

where the time fractional derivative is in Caputo's sense, according to the second equation of (1.2).

As pointed out by Caputo & Mainardi¹⁹ and Mainardi & Tomirotti,¹⁵ the creep law (2.10) is provided by viscoelastic models whose stress-strain relation (2.3) can be simply

expressed by a fractional derivative of order p (in Caputo's sense). In the present notation this stress-strain relation reads

$$\sigma = \rho a \frac{\partial^p}{\partial t^p} \epsilon, \quad 0 < p \leq 1. \quad (2.14)$$

For $p = 1$ the Newton law for a viscous fluid is recovered from (2.14) where a now represents the kinematic viscosity; in this case, since $\beta = 1$, (2.13) reduces to the classical diffusion equation (or heat equation). In the limit case $p = 0$ we obtain from (2.10) $J(t) = J_0 = 1/(\rho a)$, so from (2.6) $\psi(t) = 0$; then we recover from (2.7) the classical D'Alembert wave equation with wave-front velocity $c = \sqrt{a}$. When $0 < p < 1$ the evolution equation (2.13) can be considered intermediate between the heat equation and the wave equation. In general we refer to (2.13) with $1 < \beta < 2$ as the *time-fractional diffusion-wave equation*, and its solutions can be interpreted as *fractional diffusive waves*.^{13–15,18}

We point out that the viscoelastic models based on (2.10) or (2.14) with $0 < p < 1$ and henceforth governed by the time fractional diffusion-wave equation (2.13), are of great interest in material sciences and seismology, as far as the dissipation of the elastic energy is considered. During the deformation of a viscoelastic body, part of the total work of deformation is dissipated as heat through viscous losses but the remainder of the deformational energy is stored elastically. It is frequently of interest to determine, for a given piece of material subjected to a *sinusoidal* excitation, the total work of deformation as well as the amount of energy stored and the amount dissipated. We recall that between the sinusoidal excitation in stress, $\sigma(t) = e^{i\omega t}$, and the sinusoidal response in strain, $\epsilon(t) = J^*(\omega)e^{i\omega t}$, where

$$J^*(\omega) := i\omega \int_0^\infty J(t)e^{-i\omega t} dt = s\tilde{J}(s)|_{s=i\omega} = |J^*(\omega)|e^{-i\delta(\omega)}, \quad (2.15)$$

is the *complex compliance*, there is a *phase shift* $\delta(\omega)$. The tangent of this angle, referred to as the *loss tangent*, can be easily computed from the Laplace transform of the creep compliance. Usually, see e.g. Refs. 19, 24–25, the loss tangent is considered to be equivalent to Q^{-1} , i.e. the inverse of the *quality factor* Q , defined by

$$Q^{-1}(\omega) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\Delta W_d}{W_s^*}, \quad (2.16)$$

where ΔW_d is the amount of energy dissipated (coherently) in one cycle and W_s^* is the peak energy stored (coherently) during the cycle.

For the power-law solids we thus get from (2.10) and (2.15)

$$Q^{-1} = \tan\left(\frac{p\pi}{2}\right) \iff p = \frac{2}{\pi} \arctan(Q^{-1}). \quad (2.17)$$

As a consequence, these models exhibit a Q independent of frequency, a relevant fact pointed out by Caputo and Mainardi¹⁹ and Kjartansson.⁵ The independence of the Q from the frequency is in fact experimentally verified in pulse propagation phenomena for many materials including those of seismological interest. From (2.17) we note that the Q is also independent

of the material constants ρ and a , which, however, play a role in the phenomenon of wave dispersion.

The limit cases of absence of energy dissipation (the elastic energy is fully stored) and of absence of energy storage (the elastic energy is fully dissipated) are recovered from (2.17) for $p = 0$ (perfectly elastic solid) and $p = 1$ (perfectly viscous fluid), respectively.

As an example,¹⁵ to obtain values of seismological interest for the dissipation ($Q \approx 1000$) we need to choose the parameter p sufficiently close to zero, which corresponds to a *nearly elastic* material; from (2.17) we obtain the approximate relations between p and Q , namely

$$p \approx \left(\frac{2}{\pi Q} \right) \approx 0.64Q^{-1} \iff Q^{-1} \approx \frac{\pi}{2}p \approx 1.57p. \quad (2.18)$$

3. The Derivation of the Fundamental Solutions

In order to guarantee the existence and the uniqueness of the solution, we must equip (1.1) with suitable data on the boundary of the space-time domain. The basic boundary-value problems for diffusion are the so-called *Cauchy* and *signaling* problems. In the *Cauchy* problem, which concerns the space-time domain $-\infty < x < +\infty$, $t \geq 0$, the data are assigned at $t = 0^+$ on the whole space axis (initial data). In the *signaling* problem, which concerns the space-time domain $x \geq 0$, $t \geq 0$, the data are assigned both at $t = 0^+$ on the semi-infinite space axis $x > 0$ (initial data) and at $x = 0^+$ on the semi-infinite time axis $t > 0$ (boundary data); here, as mostly usual, the initial data are assumed to be vanishing.

Denoting by $f(x)$, $x \in \mathbf{R}$ and $h(t)$, $t \in \mathbf{R}^+$ sufficiently well-behaved functions, the basic problems are thus formulated as following, assuming $0 < \beta \leq 1$

(a) *Cauchy* problem

$$w(x, 0^+) = f(x), \quad -\infty < x < +\infty; \quad w(\mp\infty, t) = 0, \quad t > 0; \quad (3.1a)$$

(b) *signaling* problem

$$w(x, 0^+) = 0, \quad x > 0; \quad w(0^+, t) = h(t), \quad w(+\infty, t) = 0, \quad t > 0. \quad (3.1b)$$

If $1 < \beta < 2$, we must add in (3.1a) and (3.1b) the initial values of the first time derivative of the field variable, $w_t(x, 0^+)$, since in this case the fractional derivative is expressed in terms of the second-order time derivative. To ensure the continuous dependence of our solution with respect to the parameter β also in the transition from $\beta = 1^-$ to $\beta = 1^+$, we agree to assume $w_t(x, 0^+) = 0$, for $1 < \beta \leq 2$, as it turns out from the integral form (1.3)–(1.4) of our evolution equation.

In view of our subsequent analysis, essentially based on the recent review by Mainardi,¹⁸ we find it convenient to put

$$\nu = \beta/2, \quad \text{so} \quad 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad (3.2)$$

and from now on to add the parameter ν to the independent space-time variables x, t in the solutions, writing $w = w(x, t; \nu)$.

For the *Cauchy* and *signaling* problems we introduce the so-called Green functions $\mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu)$ and $\mathcal{G}_s(x, t; \nu)$, which represent the respective fundamental solutions, obtained when $f(x) = \delta(x)$ and $h(t) = \delta(t)$. As a consequence, the solutions of the two basic problems are obtained by a space or time convolution according to

$$w(x, t; \nu) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \mathcal{G}_c(x - \xi, t; \nu) f(\xi) d\xi, \quad (3.3a)$$

$$w(x, t; \nu) = \int_{0^-}^{t^+} \mathcal{G}_s(x, t - \tau; \nu) h(\tau) d\tau. \quad (3.3b)$$

It should be noted that in (3.3a) $\mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu) = \mathcal{G}_c(|x|, t; \nu)$ since the Green function of the Cauchy problem turns out to be an even function of x . According to a usual convention, in (3.3b) the limits of integration are extended to take into account for the possibility of impulse functions centered at the extremes. For the standard diffusion equation ($\nu = 1/2$) it is well known that

$$\mathcal{G}_c(x, t; 1/2) := \mathcal{G}_c^d(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi a}} t^{-1/2} e^{-x^2/(4at)}, \quad (3.4a)$$

$$\mathcal{G}_s(x, t; 1/2) := \mathcal{G}_s^d(x, t) = \frac{x}{2\sqrt{\pi a}} t^{-3/2} e^{-x^2/(4at)}. \quad (3.4b)$$

In the limit case $\nu = 1$ we recover the standard wave equation, for which, putting $c = \sqrt{a}$,

$$\mathcal{G}_c(x, t; 1) := \mathcal{G}_c^w(x, t) = \frac{1}{2} [\delta(x - ct) + \delta(x + ct)], \quad (3.5a)$$

$$\mathcal{G}_s(x, t; 1) := \mathcal{G}_s^w(x, t) = \delta(t - x/c). \quad (3.5b)$$

In the general case $0 < \nu < 1$ the two Green functions will be determined by using the technique of the Laplace transform. This technique allows us to obtain the transformed functions $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_c(x, s; \nu)$, $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_s(x, s; \nu)$, by solving ordinary differential equations of the second-order in x and then, by inversion, $\mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu)$ and $\mathcal{G}_s(x, t; \nu)$.

For the *Cauchy* problem (3.1a) with $f(x) = \delta(x)$ the application of the Laplace transform to (1.1)–(1.2) or (1.3)–(1.4) with $w(x, t) = \mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu)$ leads to the nonhomogeneous differential equation satisfied by the image of the Green function, $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_c(x, s; \nu)$,

$$a \frac{d^2 \tilde{\mathcal{G}}_c}{dx^2} - s^{2\nu} \tilde{\mathcal{G}}_c = -\delta(x) s^{2\nu-1}, \quad -\infty < x < +\infty. \quad (3.6)$$

Because of the singular term $\delta(x)$ we have to consider the above equation separately in the two intervals $x < 0$ and $x > 0$, imposing the boundary conditions at $x = \mp\infty$, $\mathcal{G}_c(\mp\infty, t; \nu) = 0$, and the necessary matching conditions at $x = 0^\pm$. We obtain

$$\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_c(x, s; \nu) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{a}s^{1-\nu}} e^{-(|x|/\sqrt{a})s^\nu}, \quad -\infty < x < +\infty. \quad (3.7)$$

For the *signaling* problem (3.1b) with $h(t) = \delta(t)$ the application of the Laplace transform to (1.1)–(1.2) or to (1.3)–(1.4) with $w(x, t) = \mathcal{G}_s(x, t; \nu)$ leads to the homogeneous differential equation

$$a \frac{d^2 \tilde{\mathcal{G}}_s}{dx^2} - s^{2\nu} \tilde{\mathcal{G}}_s = 0, \quad x \geq 0. \quad (3.8)$$

Imposing the boundary conditions at $x = 0$, $\mathcal{G}_s(0^+, t; \nu) = h(t) = \delta(t)$, and at $x = +\infty$, $\mathcal{G}_s(+\infty, t; \nu) = 0$, we obtain

$$\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_s(x, s; \nu) = e^{-(x/\sqrt{a})s^\nu}, \quad x \geq 0. \quad (3.9)$$

From (3.7) and (3.9) we recognize for the original Green functions the following *reciprocity relation*

$$2\nu x \mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu) = t \mathcal{G}_s(x, t; \nu), \quad x > 0, \quad t > 0. \quad (3.10)$$

This relation can be easily verified in the case of standard diffusion ($\nu = 1/2$), where the explicit expressions (3.4a)–(3.4b) of the Green functions lead to the identity

$$x \mathcal{G}_c^d(x, t) = t \mathcal{G}_s^d(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{x}{\sqrt{at}} e^{-x^2/(4at)} = F^d(r) = \frac{r}{2} M^d(r), \quad (3.11)$$

where

$$M^d(r) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} e^{-r^2/4}, \quad r = \frac{x}{\sqrt{at}^{1/2}} > 0. \quad (3.12)$$

The variable r is the well-known *similarity variable* whereas the two functions $F^d(r)$ and $M^d(r)$ can be considered the *auxiliary functions* for the diffusion equation because each of them provides the fundamental solutions through (3.11). We note that $M^d(r)$ satisfies the normalization condition $\int_0^\infty M^d(r) dr = 1$.

Applying in the reciprocity relation (3.10) the complex Laplace inversion formula for the transformed Green functions (3.7) and (3.9), and changing the integration variable in $\sigma = st$, we obtain

$$2\nu x \mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu) = t \mathcal{G}_s(x, t; \nu) = F(r; \nu) = \nu r M(r; \nu). \quad (3.13)$$

where

$$r = x/(\sqrt{at}^\nu) > 0 \quad (3.14)$$

is the *similarity variable* and

$$F(r; \nu) := \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{Br} e^{\sigma - r\sigma^\nu} d\sigma, \quad M(r; \nu) := \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{Br} e^{\sigma - r\sigma^\nu} \frac{d\sigma}{\sigma^{1-\nu}} \quad (3.15)$$

are the two *auxiliary functions* with $0 < \nu < 1$. In (3.15) Br denotes a Bromwich path, namely any line in the complex σ -plane defined by $\text{Re } \sigma = c > 0$.

The above definitions of $F(r; \nu)$ and $M(r; \nu)$ by the Bromwich representation can be analytically continued from $r > 0$ to any $z \in \mathbf{C}$, by deforming the Bromwich path Br into

a Hankel path Ha , a contour that begins at $\sigma = -\infty - ib$ ($b > 0$), encircles the branch cut that lies along the negative real axis, and ends up at $\sigma = -\infty + ib$.

The integral and series representations of $F(z; \nu)$ and $M(z; \nu)$, valid on all of \mathbf{C} with $0 < \nu < 1$, turn out to be

$$F(z; \nu) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{Ha} e^{\sigma - z\sigma^\nu} d\sigma, \\ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-z)^n}{n! \Gamma(-\nu n)} = -\frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-z)^n}{n!} \Gamma(\nu n + 1) \sin(\pi \nu n); \end{cases} \quad (3.16)$$

$$M(z; \nu) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{Ha} e^{\sigma - z\sigma^\nu} \frac{d\sigma}{\sigma^{1-\nu}}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-z)^n}{n! \Gamma[-\nu n + (1 - \nu)]} = \frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-z)^{n-1}}{(n-1)!} \Gamma(\nu n) \sin(\pi \nu n). \end{cases} \quad (3.17)$$

In the theory of special functions,²⁶ we find an entire function, referred to as the *Wright function*, which reads (in our notation)

$$W_{\lambda, \mu}(z) := \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{Ha} e^{\sigma + z\sigma^{-\lambda}} \frac{d\sigma}{\sigma^\mu} := \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{n! \Gamma(\lambda n + \mu)}, \quad z \in \mathbf{C}, \quad (3.18)$$

where $\lambda > -1$ and $\mu > 0$. From a comparison among (3.16)–(3.17) and (3.18) we recognize that the auxiliary functions are related to the Wright function according to

$$F(z; \nu) = W_{-\nu, 0}(-z) = \nu z M(z; \nu), \quad M(z; \nu) = W_{-\nu, 1-\nu}(-z). \quad (3.19)$$

Although convergent in all of \mathbf{C} , the series representations in (3.16)–(3.17) can be used to provide a numerical evaluation of our auxiliary functions only for relatively small values of r , so that asymptotic evaluations as $r \rightarrow +\infty$ are required. Choosing as a variable r/ν rather than r , the computation by the saddle-point method for the M function is easier and yields.

$$M(r/\nu; \nu) \sim \frac{r^{(\nu-1/2)/(1-\nu)}}{\sqrt{2\pi(1-\nu)}} \exp \left[-\frac{1-\nu}{\nu} r^{1/(1-\nu)} \right], \quad r \rightarrow +\infty. \quad (3.20)$$

We note that the saddle-point method for $\nu = 1/2$ provides the exact result (3.12), i.e., $M(r; 1/2) = M^d(r) = (1/\sqrt{\pi}) \exp(-r^2/4)$, but breaks down for $\nu \rightarrow 1^-$. The case $\nu = 1$, for which (1.1) reduces to the standard wave equation, is of course a singular limit also for the series representation since $M(r; 1) = \delta(r - 1)$.

The exponential decay for $r \rightarrow +\infty$ ensures that all the moments of $M(r; \nu)$ in \mathbf{R}^+ are finite; we obtain

$$\int_0^{+\infty} r^n M(r; \nu) dr = \frac{\Gamma(n+1)}{\Gamma(\nu n + 1)}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (3.21)$$

4. The Scaling Properties and the Evolution of the Fundamental Solutions

It is known that in theoretical seismology the Dirac delta-function is of great relevance in simulating the pulse generated by an ideal seismic source, concentrated in space, $\delta(x)$, or in time, $\delta(t)$. Consequently, the fundamental solutions of the *Cauchy* and *signaling* problems are those of greater interest because they provide us with information on the possible evolution of the seismic pulses during their propagation from the seismic source. Accounting of the reciprocity relation (3.13) and the similarity variable (3.14), $r = x/(\sqrt{at}^\nu)$, the two fundamental solutions can be written, for $x > 0$ and $t > 0$, as

$$\mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu) = \frac{1}{2\nu x} F(r; \nu) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{at}^\nu} M(r; \nu), \quad (4.1)$$

$$\mathcal{G}_s(x, t; \nu) = \frac{1}{t} F(r; \nu) = \frac{\nu x}{\sqrt{at}^{1+\nu}} M(r; \nu). \quad (4.2)$$

The two fundamental solutions exhibit scaling properties that make easier their plots versus distance (at fixed instant) and versus time (at fixed position). In fact the above equations mean that for the fundamental solution of the *Cauchy* [*signaling*] problem the time [spatial] shape is the same at each position [instant], the only changes being due to space [time] — dependent changes of width and amplitude. The maximum amplitude in time [space] varies precisely as $1/x$ [$1/t$].

We also note the exponential decay of $\mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu)$ as $x \rightarrow +\infty$ (at fixed t) and the algebraic decay of $\mathcal{G}_s(x, t; \nu)$ as $t \rightarrow +\infty$ (at fixed x), for $0 < \nu < 1$. In fact, using (4.1a)–(4.1b) with (3.17) and (3.20), we get

$$\mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu) \sim A(t)x^{(\nu-1/2)/(1-\nu)} \exp[-B(t)x^{1/(1-\nu)}], \quad x \rightarrow \infty, \quad (4.3)$$

$$\mathcal{G}_s(x, t; \nu) \sim C(x)t^{-(1+\nu)}, \quad t \rightarrow \infty, \quad (4.4)$$

where $A(t)$, $B(t)$ and $C(x)$ are positive functions.

In Fig. 1, as an example, we compare versus $|x|$, at fixed t , the fundamental solutions of the *Cauchy* problem with different ν ($\nu = 1/4, 1/2, 3/4$). We consider the range $0 \leq |x| \leq 4$ and assume $a = t = 1$.

In the limit cases $\nu = 0$ and $\nu = 1$ we have

$$\mathcal{G}_c(x, t; 0) = \frac{e^{-|x|}}{2}, \quad \mathcal{G}_c(x, t; 1) = \frac{\delta(x - \sqrt{at}) + \delta(x + \sqrt{at})}{2}. \quad (4.5)$$

In Fig. 2, as an example, we compare versus t , at fixed x , the fundamental solutions of the *signaling* problem with different ν ($\nu = 1/4, 1/2, 3/4$). We consider the range $0 \leq t \leq 3$ and assume $a = x = 1$.

In the limit cases $\nu = 0, 1$, we have

$$\mathcal{G}_s(x, t; 0) = \delta(t), \quad \mathcal{G}_s(x, t; 1) = \delta(t - x/\sqrt{a}). \quad (4.6)$$

Fig. 1. The Cauchy problem for the time-fractional diffusion equation. The fundamental solutions versus $|x|$, at $t = 1$, with (a) $\nu = 1/4$, (b) $\nu = 1/2$, (c) $\nu = 3/4$.

Fig. 2. The signaling problem for the time-fractional diffusion equation. The fundamental solutions versus t , at $x = 1$, with (a) $\nu = 1/4$, (b) $\nu = 1/2$, (c) $\nu = 3/4$.

In order to inspect the evolution of the initial pulse for seismological purposes, we need to plot $\mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu)$ versus x and $\mathcal{G}_s(x, t; \nu)$ versus t as ν is sufficiently close to 1 (*nearly elastic* cases) to ensure a sufficiently low value for the constant internal friction Q^{-1} . From (2.13)–(2.14) and (2.16)–(2.17) we need to consider $\nu = 1 - \epsilon$ with $\epsilon = \nu/2$ of the order of 0.001 to 0.01. In the evaluation of the auxiliary functions in the *nearly elastic* cases, we note that the matching between the series and saddle point representations is no longer achieved since the saddle point turns out to be wide and the consequent approximation becomes poor. In these cases we refer the reader to Mainardi & Tomirotti¹⁵ where the authors have adopted the ingenious variant of the saddle-point method introduced by Pipkin,^{6–7} which allows one to see some structure in the peak while it tends to the Dirac delta function.

5. The Fundamental Solutions as Probability Density Functions

It is well-known that the fundamental solution of the standard diffusion equation for the Cauchy problem is related with the *Gauss* or *normal* probability law, bilateral in space. In fact, recalling (3.4a), we have

$$\mathcal{G}_c^d(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi at}} e^{-x^2/(4at)} = p_G(x; \sigma), \quad (5.1)$$

where

$$p_G(x; \sigma) := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-x^2/(2\sigma^2)}, \quad \sigma^2 = 2at, \quad (5.2)$$

denotes the well-known *Gauss* probability density function (*pdf*) with variance σ^2 . The associated cumulative distribution function is known to be

$$\mathcal{P}_G(x; \sigma) := \int_{-\infty}^x p_G(x; \sigma) dx = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \right) \right] = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{at}} \right) \right]. \quad (5.3)$$

The moments of even order of the *Gauss pdf* turn out to be

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x^{2n} p_G(x; \sigma) dx = \frac{(2n)!}{2^n n!} \sigma^{2n} = (2n-1)!! \sigma^{2n} = (2n-1)!! (2at)^n, \quad n \in \mathbf{N}. \quad (5.4)$$

If we consider the fundamental solution of the standard diffusion equation for the signaling problem, we note that it is related to the *Lévy-Smirnov* probability law, unilateral in time. In fact, recalling (3.4b), we have

$$\mathcal{G}_s^d(x, t) = \frac{x}{2\sqrt{\pi at^{3/2}}} e^{-x^2/(4at)} = p_L(t; \mu), \quad (5.5)$$

where

$$p_L(t; \mu) = \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{\sqrt{2\pi t^{3/2}}} e^{-\mu/(2t)}, \quad \mu = \frac{x^2}{2a}, \quad (5.6)$$

denotes the *Lévy-Smirnov pdf*,²⁷ with cumulative distribution function

$$\mathcal{P}_L(t; \mu) := \int_0^t p_L(t; \mu) dt = \operatorname{erfc} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\mu}{2t}} \right) = \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{at}} \right). \quad (5.7)$$

For the *Lévy-Smirnov pdf* all moments of positive integer order are infinite, since it decays at infinity as $t^{-3/2}$. However, we note that the moments of real order δ are finite only if $\delta < 1/2$. In particular, for this *pdf* the mean (the moment of order 1) is infinite, so we can take the *median* instead of the expectation value. From $\mathcal{P}_L(t_{\text{med}}; \mu) = 1/2$, it turns out that $t_{\text{med}} \approx 2\mu$, since the complementary error function takes on the value 1/2 as its argument is approximatively 1/2.

The *Gauss* and *Lévy-Smirnov* laws are special cases of the important class of *stable* probability distributions with index of stability (or characteristic exponent) $\alpha = 2$ and $\alpha = 1/2$, respectively. Another special case is provided by the Cauchy law with *pdf* $p_C(x; \lambda) = \lambda/[\pi(x^2 + \lambda^2)]$ whose index of stability is $\alpha = 1$.

For the general theory of the α — stable distributions we refer the reader to specialized treatises, see e.g., Refs. 27–29. The systematic research on stable distributions was started by Paul Lévy in the twenties: the inspiration was the desire to generalize the celebrated *Central Limit Theorem*: in fact these distributions are proved to be the only distributions which have their own *domain of attraction*.

Here we limit ourselves to recall their essential properties relevant for this paper. The name *stable* has been assigned to these distributions because of the following property: if two independent real random variables with the same shape or *type* of distribution are combined linearly and the distribution of the resulting random variable has the same shape, the common distribution (or its type, more precisely) is said to be *stable*. More precisely, if Y_1 and Y_2 are random variables having such distribution, then Y defined by the linear combination $cY = c_1Y_1 + c_2Y_2$ has a similar distribution with the same index α for any positive real values of the constants c, c_1 and c_2 with $c^\alpha = c_1^\alpha + c_2^\alpha$. As a matter of fact only the range $0 < \alpha \leq 2$ is allowed for the index of stability. The case $\alpha = 2$ is noteworthy since it corresponds to the *normal* distribution, which is the only stable distribution which has finite variance, indeed finite moments of any order. In the cases $0 < \alpha < 2$ the corresponding *pdf* $p_\alpha(y)$ exhibit fat tails in that $\int_{|y|>\lambda} p_\alpha(y)dy = O(\lambda^{-\alpha})$; consequently their absolute moments of order δ are finite if $0 \leq \delta < \alpha$ and infinite if $\delta \geq \alpha$.

An α — stable distribution is also *infinitely divisible*, i.e. for every positive integer n its characteristic function (the Fourier transform of its *pdf*) can be expressed as the n th power of the characteristic function of a certain probability distribution, which in this case is α — stable as well. All stable *pdf* are *unimodal* and indeed *bell-shaped*, i.e. their n th derivative has exactly n zeros. Furthermore, for $\alpha \neq 2$, they can be asymmetric with respect to their maximum.

According to the simplified parameterization by Feller,²⁷ the α -*stable* distributions turn out to depend on an additional single parameter θ related to the asymmetry, said (improperly) the *skewness*. The skewness parameter turns out to be restricted as follows: $|\theta| \leq \alpha$ if $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $|\theta| \leq 2 - \alpha$ if $1 < \alpha \leq 2$.

Denoting from now on an α — stable *pdf* (associated to the real random variable Y) by $p_\alpha(y; \theta)$, we note the property $p_\alpha(-y; -\theta) = p_\alpha(y; \theta)$. Consequently a stable *pdf* with $\theta = 0$ is necessarily symmetrical.

For $\alpha \neq 2$ stable distributions with extremal values of θ are called *extremal*. From the theory one recognizes that all the extremal stable distributions with $0 < \alpha < 1$ are unilateral, i.e. vanishing in \mathbf{R}^\pm if $\theta = \pm\alpha$. Furthermore, the following representations by convergent power series can be derived for stable distributions with $0 < \alpha < 1$ (negative powers) and $1 < \alpha < 2$ (positive powers), for $y > 0$,

$$p_\alpha(y; \theta) = \frac{1}{\pi y} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-y^{-\alpha})^n \frac{\Gamma(n\alpha + 1)}{n!} \sin \left[\frac{n\pi}{2}(\theta - \alpha) \right], \quad 0 < \alpha < 1, \quad (5.8)$$

$$p_\alpha(y; \theta) = \frac{1}{\pi y} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-y)^n \frac{\Gamma(n/\alpha + 1)}{n!} \sin \left[\frac{n\pi}{2\alpha}(\theta - \alpha) \right], \quad 1 < \alpha < 2. \quad (5.9)$$

It has been shown that the two series in (5.8)–(5.9) provide also the asymptotic (divergent) expansions to the stable *pdf* with the ranges of α interchanged from those of convergence, that is the series at the R.H.S of (5.8) is asymptotic for the L.H.S of (5.9) as $y \rightarrow \infty$, and the series at the R.H.S. of (5.9) is asymptotic for the L.H.S of (5.8) as $y \rightarrow 0$.

From (5.8)–(5.9) a relation between stable *pdf* with index α and $1/\alpha$, can be derived. Assuming $1/2 < \alpha < 1$ and $y > 0$, we obtain

$$\frac{1}{y^{\alpha+1}} p_{1/\alpha}(y^{-\alpha}; \theta) = p_{\alpha}(y; \theta^*), \quad \theta^* = \alpha(\theta + 1) - 1. \quad (5.10)$$

A quick check shows that θ^* falls within the prescribed range, $|\theta^*| \leq \alpha$, provided that $|\theta| \leq 2 - 1/\alpha$. Furthermore, we can derive a relation between extremal stable *pdf* and our auxiliary functions of Wright type. In fact, by comparing (5.8)–(5.9) with the series representations in (3.15)–(3.16) and using (3.18), we obtain

$$p_{\alpha}(y; -\alpha) = \frac{1}{y} F(y^{-\alpha}; \alpha) = \frac{\alpha}{y^{\alpha+1}} M(y^{-\alpha}; \alpha), \quad 0 < \alpha < 1, \quad (5.11)$$

$$p_{\alpha}(y; \alpha - 2) = \frac{1}{y} F(y; 1/\alpha) = \frac{1}{\alpha} M(y; 1/\alpha), \quad 1 < \alpha < 2. \quad (5.12)$$

Consequently we can interpret the fundamental solutions (4.1) and (4.2) in terms of stable *pdf*, so generalizing the arguments for the standard diffusion equation based on (5.1)–(5.7).

We easily recognize that for $0 < \nu < 1$ the fundamental solution for the signaling problem provides a unilateral extremal stable *pdf* in (scaled) time with index of stability $\alpha = \nu$, which decays according to (4.4) with a power law. In fact, from (4.2) and (5.11) we note that, putting $y = r^{-1/\nu} = \tau$,

$$(x/\sqrt{a})^{1/\nu} \mathcal{G}_s(x, t; \nu) = p_{\nu}(\tau; -\nu), \quad \tau = t(\sqrt{a}/x)^{1/\nu} > 0. \quad (5.13)$$

This property has been noted also by Kreiss and Pipkin⁶ based on (3.9) and on Feller's result, $p_{\alpha}(t; -\alpha) \div \exp(-s^{\alpha})$ for $0 < \alpha < 1$.

As far as the Cauchy problem is concerned, we note that the corresponding fundamental solution provides a bilateral symmetrical *pdf* in (scaled) distance with two branches, for $x > 0$ and $x < 0$, obtained one from the other by reflection. For large $|x|$ each branch exhibits an exponential decay according to (4.3) and, only for $1/2 \leq \nu < 1$, it is the corresponding branch of an extremal stable *pdf* with index of stability $\alpha = 1/\nu$. In fact, from (4.2) and (5.12) we note that, putting $y = |r| = \xi > 0$,

$$2\nu\sqrt{at}^{\nu} \mathcal{G}_c(|x|, t; \nu) = p_{1/\nu}(\xi, 1/\nu - 2), \quad \xi = |x|/(\sqrt{at}^{\nu}) > 0. \quad (5.14)$$

This property generalizes the Gaussian property of the *pdf* found for $\nu = 1/2$ (standard diffusion). Furthermore, using (3.21), the moments (of even order) of $\mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu)$ turn out to be

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x^{2n} \mathcal{G}_c(x, t; \nu) dx = \frac{\Gamma(2n+1)}{\Gamma(2\nu n+1)} (at^{2\nu})^n, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (5.15)$$

We recognize that the variance is now proportional to $at^{2\nu}$, namely $\sigma^2 \sim t^{\beta}$, which implies a phenomenon of *anomalous diffusion* for $\beta \neq 1$, i.e. slow diffusion for $0 < \beta < 1$ and fast diffusion for $1 < \beta < 2$.

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Appendix A. Essentials of Fractional Calculus

Fractional calculus is the field of mathematical analysis which deals with the investigation and applications of integrals and derivatives of arbitrary order. The term *fractional* is a misnomer, but it is retained following the prevailing use.

The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral

According to the Riemann-Liouville approach to fractional calculus, the notion of fractional integral of order α ($\alpha > 0$) is a natural consequence of the well-known formula (usually attributed to Cauchy), that reduces the calculation of the n -fold primitive of a function $f(t)$ to a single integral of convolution type. In our notation the Cauchy formula reads

$$I^n f(t) := f_n(t) = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{n-1} f(\tau) d\tau, \quad t > 0, \quad n \in \mathbf{N}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where \mathbf{N} is the set of positive integers. From this definition we note that $f_n(t)$ vanishes at $t = 0$ with its derivatives of order $1, 2, \dots, n-1$. For convention we require that $f(t)$ and henceforth $f_n(t)$ be a *causal* function, i.e. identically vanishing for $t < 0$.

In a natural way one is led to extend the above formula from positive integer values of the index to any positive real values by using the Gamma function. Indeed, noting that $(n-1)! = \Gamma(n)$, and introducing the arbitrary *positive* real number α , one defines the *Fractional Integral of order $\alpha > 0$* :

$$I^\alpha f(t) := \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau, \quad t > 0, \quad \alpha \in \mathbf{R}^+, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where \mathbf{R}^+ is the set of positive real numbers. For complementation we define $I^0 := \mathbf{I}$ (Identity operator), i.e. we mean $I^0 f(t) = f(t)$. Furthermore, by $I^\alpha f(0^+)$ we mean the limit (if it exists) of $I^\alpha f(t)$ for $t \rightarrow 0^+$; this limit may be infinite.

We note the *semigroup property* $I^\alpha I^\beta = I^{\alpha+\beta}$, $\alpha, \beta \geq 0$, which implies the *commutative property* $I^\beta I^\alpha = I^\alpha I^\beta$, and the effect of our operators I^α on the power functions

$$I^\alpha t^\gamma = \frac{\Gamma(\gamma+1)}{\Gamma(\gamma+1+\alpha)} t^{\gamma+\alpha}, \quad \alpha \geq 0, \quad \gamma > -1, \quad t > 0. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

These properties are of course a natural generalization of those known when the order is a positive integer.

Introducing the Laplace transform by the notation $\mathcal{L}[f(t); s] := \int_0^\infty e^{-st} f(t) dt = \tilde{f}(s)$, $s \in \mathbf{C}$, and using the sign \div to denote a Laplace transform pair, i.e. $f(t) \div \tilde{f}(s)$, we note

the following rule for the Laplace transform of the fractional integral,

$$I^\alpha f(t) \doteq \frac{\tilde{f}(s)}{s^\alpha}, \quad \alpha \geq 0, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

which is the generalization of the case with an n -fold repeated integral.

The Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative

After the notion of fractional integral, that of fractional derivative of order α ($\alpha > 0$) becomes a natural requirement and one is attempted to substitute α with $-\alpha$ in the above formulas. However, this generalization needs some care in order to guarantee the convergence of the integrals and preserve the well-known properties of the ordinary derivative of integer order.

Denoting by D^n with $n \in \mathbf{N}$ the operator of the derivative of order n , we first note that $D^n I^n = \mathbf{I}$, $I^n D^n \neq \mathbf{I}$, $n \in \mathbf{N}$ i.e. D^n is left-inverse (and not right-inverse) to the corresponding integral operator J^n . In fact we easily recognize from (A.1) that

$$I^n D^n f(t) = f(t) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} f^{(k)}(0^+) \frac{t^k}{k!}, \quad t > 0. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

As a consequence, we expect that D^α is defined as left-inverse to I^α . For this purpose, introducing the positive integer m such that $m-1 < \alpha \leq m$, and noting that $(D^m I^{m-\alpha}) I^\alpha = D^m (I^{m-\alpha} I^\alpha) = D^m I^m = \mathbf{I}$, we define *Fractional Derivative of order $\alpha > 0$* as $D^\alpha := D^m I^{m-\alpha}$, namely

$$D^\alpha f(t) := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \frac{d^m}{dt^m} \int_0^t \frac{f(\tau)}{(t-\tau)^{\alpha+1-m}} d\tau, & m-1 < \alpha < m, \\ \frac{d^m}{dt^m} f(t), & \alpha = m. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

For $\alpha \rightarrow m^-$ we thus recover the standard derivative of order m but the integral formula loses its meaning for $\alpha = m$. Defining for complementation $D^0 = I^0 = \mathbf{I}$, then we easily recognize that for $\alpha \geq 0$

$$D^\alpha t^\gamma = \frac{\Gamma(\gamma+1)}{\Gamma(\gamma+1-\alpha)} t^{\gamma-\alpha}, \quad \alpha \geq 0, \quad \gamma > -1, \quad t > 0. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Of course, these properties are a natural generalization of those known when the order is a positive integer. Note the remarkable fact that the fractional derivative $D^\alpha f$ is not zero for the constant function $f(t) \equiv 1$ if $\alpha \notin \mathbf{N}$. In fact, (A.7) with $\gamma = 0$ teaches us that

$$D^\alpha 1 = \frac{t^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)}, \quad \alpha \geq 0, \quad t > 0. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

This, of course, is $\equiv 0$ for $\alpha \in \mathbf{N}$, due to the poles of the gamma function in the points $0, -1, -2, \dots$

The Caputo fractional derivative

We now observe that an alternative definition of fractional derivative, originally introduced by Caputo,^{1,30} in the late sixties and adopted by Caputo and Mainardi¹⁹ in the framework of the theory of *Linear Viscoelasticity*, is $D_*^\alpha = I^{m-\alpha}D^m$ with $m - 1 < \alpha \leq m$, namely

$$D_*^\alpha f(t) := \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \int_0^t \frac{f^{(m)}(\tau)}{(t-\tau)^{\alpha+1-m}} d\tau, & m-1 < \alpha < m, \\ \frac{d^m}{dt^m} f(t), & \alpha = m. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

This definition is of course more restrictive than (A.6), in that requires the absolute integrability of the derivative of order m . Whenever we use the operator D_*^α we (tacitly) assume that this condition is met. We easily recognize that in general

$$D^\alpha f(t) := D^m I^{m-\alpha} f(t) \neq I^{m-\alpha} D^m f(t) := D_*^\alpha f(t), \quad (\text{A.10})$$

unless the function $f(t)$ along with its first $m - 1$ derivatives vanishes at $t = 0^+$. In fact, assuming that the passage of the m -derivative under the integral is legitimate, one recognizes that, for $m - 1 < \alpha < m$ and $t > 0$,

$$D^\alpha f(t) = D_*^\alpha f(t) + \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{t^{k-\alpha}}{\Gamma(k-\alpha+1)} f^{(k)}(0^+), \quad (\text{A.11})$$

and therefore, recalling the fractional derivative of the power functions (A.7),

$$D^\alpha \left(f(t) - \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{t^k}{k!} f^{(k)}(0^+) \right) = D_*^\alpha f(t). \quad (\text{A.12})$$

The alternative definition (A.9) for the fractional derivative thus incorporates the initial values of the function and of its integer derivatives of lower order. The subtraction of the Taylor polynomial of degree $m - 1$ at $t = 0^+$ from $f(t)$ means a sort of regularization of the fractional derivative. In particular, according to this definition, the relevant property for which the fractional derivative of a constant is still zero can be easily recognized, i.e.

$$D_*^\alpha 1 \equiv 0, \quad \alpha > 0. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

We now explore the most relevant differences between the two fractional derivatives (A.6) and (A.9). We agree to denote (A.9) as the *Caputo fractional derivative* to distinguish it from the standard Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative (A.6). We observe, again by looking at (A.7), that $D^\alpha t^{\alpha-1} \equiv 0$, $\alpha > 0$, $t > 0$. From above we thus recognize the following statements about functions that for $t > 0$ admit the same fractional derivative of order α , with $m - 1 < \alpha \leq m$, $m \in \mathbf{N}$,

$$D^\alpha f(t) = D^\alpha g(t) \iff f(t) = g(t) + \sum_{j=1}^m c_j t^{\alpha-j}, \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$D_*^\alpha f(t) = D_*^\alpha g(t) \iff f(t) = g(t) + \sum_{j=1}^m c_j t^{m-j}. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

In these formulas the coefficients c_j are arbitrary constants.

For the two definitions we also note a difference with respect to the *formal* limit as $\alpha \rightarrow (m-1)^+$. From (A.6) and (A.9) we obtain respectively,

$$\alpha \rightarrow (m-1)^+ \implies D^\alpha f(t) \rightarrow D^m I f(t) = D^{m-1} f(t); \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$\alpha \rightarrow (m-1)^+ \implies D_*^\alpha f(t) \rightarrow I D^m f(t) = D^{m-1} f(t) - f^{(m-1)}(0^+). \quad (\text{A.17})$$

We now consider the *Laplace transforms* of the two fractional derivatives. For the standard fractional derivative D^α the Laplace transform, assumed to exist, requires the knowledge of the (bounded) initial values of the fractional integral $I^{m-\alpha} f(t)$ and of its integer derivatives of order $k = 1, 2, \dots, m-1$. The corresponding rule reads, in our notation,

$$D^\alpha f(t) \div s^\alpha \tilde{f}(s) - \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} D^k I^{(m-\alpha)} f(0^+) s^{m-1-k}, \quad m-1 < \alpha \leq m. \quad (\text{A.18})$$

The *Caputo fractional derivative* appears more suitable to be treated by the Laplace transform technique in that it requires the knowledge of the (bounded) initial values of the function and of its integer derivatives of order $k = 1, 2, \dots, m-1$, in analogy with the case when $\alpha = m$. In fact, by using (A.4) and noting that

$$I^\alpha D_*^\alpha f(t) = I^\alpha I^{m-\alpha} D^m f(t) = I^m D^m f(t) = f(t) - \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} f^{(k)}(0^+) \frac{t^k}{k!}, \quad (\text{A.19})$$

we easily prove the following rule for the Laplace transform,

$$D_*^\alpha f(t) \div s^\alpha \tilde{f}(s) - \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} f^{(k)}(0^+) s^{\alpha-1-k}, \quad m-1 < \alpha \leq m. \quad (\text{A.20})$$

Indeed, the result (A.20), first stated by Caputo¹ by using the Fubini-Tonelli theorem, appears as the most “natural” generalization of the corresponding result well-known for $\alpha = m$.

Biographical remarks

This appendix is based on the review by Gorenflo & Mainardi.³¹ For more details on the theory and applications of fractional calculus the reader is referred e.g. Refs. 1, 31–37. In particular, Gorenflo & Mainardi³¹ and Podlubny³⁷ have pointed out the major utility of the Caputo fractional derivative in the treatment of differential equations of fractional order for *physical applications*. In fact, in physical problems, the initial conditions are usually expressed in terms of a given number of bounded values assumed by the field variable and its derivatives of integer order, no matter if the governing evolution equation may be a generic integro-differential equation and therefore, in particular, a fractional differential equation.

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